

Review

The Effect of Covid-19 on Employee's Mental Health: A Literature Review

Elizabeth Elias^{1*}, Emilia Landa Shikomba²

¹School of Business Administration, Dongbei University of Finance and Economics, China

²School of Business Administration, Chongqing University, China

***Corresponding author**

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Abstract: *Due to the complexity of pandemics and lack of information about the epidemiology of pandemic-related mental health problems and the possible approaches to resolve them. The occurrence of mental health problems during a pandemic may be assumed but difficult to address. When Covid-19 hurred in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China by the end of December 2019 the whole country was locked up and everyone in China was put in quarantine to prevent further viral spread. All activities and productions had been suspended, non-essential workplaces, schools and universities had also been closed. This was challenging to mental health for everyone, as Covid-19 came with stressors which include; financial loss and job insecurity, death, loosing of properties and more. Covid-19 stressors had increased mental breakdown of employees as they are stressed by all the stressful happenings in the pandemic. However, the pandemic led to the struggle with psychological health due to the fear of Covid-19, which included depression, anxiety and boredom. This study discusses the effect of Covid-19 on employee's mental health through the analysis of this relationship. In so, doing, articles concerning employee's mental health related to the Covid-19 outbreak and other previous global infections have been considered and reviewed. The identified literature reported a positive impact of Covid-19 on employee's mental health. In the findings of the study, people lack understanding on the danger of mental breakdown and need awareness on mental health. Therefore, the study recommends mental health education to be offered through all convenient platforms that can help people learn and strengthen their mental health during the pandemic. Besides, employers need to pay more attention to employee's mental health problems, particularly depression and anxiety among employees and combating with pandemic while fighting public health crises. Mental health professionals, such as psychologists, psychiatrists and social workers, must be on the front line as they need to play a leading role in emergency planning and management teams. Counselling services need to be made available and free for employees, more investment should be on counselling and psychology centers in this pandemic.*

Keywords: Covid-19, Mental Health, Depression, Anxiety, Employees, Pandemic

Introduction

Sixteen years after the epidemic of severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) in Guangdong province, another highly pathogenic coronavirus, the corona virus disease 2019 (Covid-19) emerged in mid-December 2019, in Wuhan, Hubei province, China (Tang, et al., 2020). In effect, late December 2019, patients in Wuhan, China, testified having viral pneumonia due to an unknown microbial pathogen which had caused chaos in China and the worldwide (Liang, et al., 2020). The experts from the National Health Commission were sent to Wuhan to investigate in the Laboratory of Virology, Chinese Center for Disease Control and Prevention on 7 January 2020 and discovered out the virus which is called Novel Coronavirus (Covid-19) (Wang, et al., 2020). These medical investigations confirmed that coronavirus is not only a physical health's risk, but it also weighs heavily on the mental health of individuals. In addition, the incidence on suicide of a 37-year-old government worker, in Japan, who was responsible for looking after isolated returnees from Wuhan (China) (The Japan Times, 2020) confirmed that hypothesis. The mental health problems associated with this global event can develop into long-term health issues, depression and boredom.

Considering these previous assumptions, this paper examines the effects of Covid-19 pandemic on employee's mental health by reviewing different papers that are written on the subject. The aims of this paper are two-fold, firstly to study the influence of Covid-19 on the mental health of workers in organizations. Secondly, to assess the key organizational interventions that can minimize this effect. This paper contributes to the literature on this question by showing the importance of mental health issues, especially in this pandemic period. In the next sections of this study, I respectively present the evolution of the literature about this question, then the methodology of my analysis, followed by the results of the discussion, then the conclusion.

Materials and methods

Literature Review

This part recapitulates relevant literature on effect of Covid-19 on employee's mental health. It brings out the depth of effects of pandemics in general, Covid-19 on mental health and mitigating factors of Covid-19 on employee's mental health.

According to (Aqui & Miguel, 2020) the novel coronavirus was first discovered in China, and it rapidly spread around the globe where all the countries went on lockdown with the aim to contain and control the pandemic. And on the 14th June 2020 the confirmed cases of Covid-19 stand at 7,859,557 active cases, deaths stand at 432,168 and 4,025,519 recoveries (Worldometers, 2020). The virus which is human to human transmission has kept people a distance from each other to avoid the spread. The pandemic has caused panic from all sectors of all production worldwide. Furthermore, the impact is not only on production, it has also affected the mental health of employees and the whole population in general.

The outbreak created worldwide chaos on lockdown stated by (Salcedo & Cherehus, 2020) and everyone obeyed to the rules and regulations to avoid the spread of the virus. However, the pandemic caused some mental health challenges amongst us, according to (Holmes, et al., 2020) the 2019 pandemic (Covid-19) has a significant impact on all aspects of life, including mental health and physical health. A recent study by (Qiu, Shen, & Zhao, 2020) made it clear that the Covid-19 pandemic had caused serious threats to people's physical and mental health. It also caused a wide variety of psychological problems, such as panic disorder, anxiety and depression to mention a few. This pandemic affected everyone including university students, heightened levels of psychological distress and downstream negative academic consequences are prevalent under normal circumstances (Grubic, Badovinac, & Amer, 2020).

Mental health

According to World Health Organization (2020), mental health was defined as a state of well-being in which an individual realizes his or her own abilities to cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community. In addition, mental health is referred in another context by way of perceptual, compartmental and emotional well-being. Everything is about the way people think, feel and act Medical News Today, (2020). Sometimes the word "mental health" is used to mean the lack of a mental disorder. Mental health is a major concern of everyone and a recent study by Yao et al. (2020) showed that the feelings of the Covid-19 could impact the mental health in patients more intensely and everyone affected, resulting in recurrences of already existing health issues or the establishment of new mental health conditions due to high stress and vulnerability to the general population.

Effects of pandemics in general

During the SARS outbreak in 2003, many people suffered from poor sleep and short sleep durations because of anxiety and depressive symptoms (Chen et al., 2006; Johal, 2009), it is reasonable to assume that higher exposure led to less sleep, which in return increased the risk of mental illness. According to Yip (2010), the outbreak of severe acute respiratory syndrome in 2003 was linked with a 30 % increase in suicide within patients 65 and older; approximately 50% of patients recovering were depressed, and 29% of healthcare workers were likely to experience an uptick emotional distress.

During the 2013-2016 Ebola virus epidemic caused psychological effects due to the psychological effect due to the traumatic course of the infection, fear of death and experience or witnessing others dying and the guiltiness of helpless to others. Additionally, during the Middle East Respiratory Syndrome epidemic, 80.2% of the general public reported emotional distress influenced by the stressors in the pandemic (Jeong, et al., 2016). In concurrence, all pandemics have an effect on mental health. The pandemic fear can influence people who do not have historical poor mental health. People with chronic mental health problems, particularly people with severe mental disorders, may be particularly affected by deterioration, disorders in health, loneliness, possible symptom exacerbation as a result of pandemic facts and conducts, as well as changes in mental health legislation.

The risk of post - traumatic stress and depression is in patients who survived serious and life - threatening illnesses (Tsang et al. 2004). Many of the expected consequences of quarantine and related social and physical exclusion steps are major risk factors for mental health concerns themselves. For Holmes et al., (2020), pandemics bring fear of life which increase suicide and self - harming, alcohol and drug usage, abuse, addiction, violence in the household and in children and psychosocial risks (for example social detachment, lack of sense or paradox, pit, cyberbullying, burden-felting, financial stress, degradation, loss, joblessness, unemployment and a breakdown in many relationships). People with learning problems and neuro-developmental disorders may experience changes in treatment and behavior, soul and depression, illness and pain. Schools and universities closures in the pandemic can affect kids and students because of the dysfunctional households they live in, as they are the young people and children hiding place. The pandemic has driven some to gain addiction to substance abuse, alcohol, domestic violence,

child abuse, lack of free school food, housing, overcrowding, disruption and interruption to parental and social work networks. Elderly people and those with multi-morbidities are particularly influenced by the so-called digital divide, including loneliness, depression, end of life and poverty. Keeping a balance on financial loss and job insecurities is one of the challenges of the pandemics as many countries go on the lockdown, business closure and losing jobs is on an increase. The Covid-19 pandemic may cause abnormalities in the general public as well because it is more intense in infecting and killing individual, the next subdivision discusses this.

Mental health during Covid-19

The link between Covid-19 and mental health can be considered as positive according to different authors. In effect, Tang et al. (2020) showed in their study that, the Covid-19 outbreak has brought so much fear and caused psychological distress, this changed the sleeping patterns of many people, as they stay all the nights awake and sleep few hours worried if they are next to be infected by the virus. Holmes et al. (2020), considered that collective issues have an impact on daily actions, economics, prevention strategies and policy makers, health organizations and medical centers, which can disrupt Covid-19, control strategies and can lead to increased global morbidity and mental health needs.

For Gao et al. (2020), the time of the Covid-19 pandemic is the same time people are spreading different information on social media that can cause panic among the people. Some social media users have been sharing irrelevant information on the rise of cases and people are at the stage of believing all information as true even the ones that are not confirmed, leading to badly affecting other people's mental health. So, during this period, social media led to an overburden (mis)information, which in return really caused mental health problems because people are already in fear. Additionally, World Health Organization (2020) has pointed out that the drivers of fear, anxiety and stigma, fuel misinformation and rumor are mainly youth especially on social media.

The previous studies of Neria & Sullivan (2011) have demonstrated that the original levels of after-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) symptoms can be improved by unintentional social media exposure. Venkatesh & Edirrapuli (2020) concluded that anxiety might arise from fear of contagion and insufficient clarity around guidelines and regulations, often made worse by less reliable media sources heightening confusion and fearmongering. No one is exempted from the

mental disorders that come with the pandemic and Kang, et al., (2020) study is an indication that the population especially the nurses and doctors have higher rates of anxiety and stress symptoms, including psychiatric disorders like post - traumatic stress, which increase the need for treatment. For Holmes, et al., (2020) health care workers at the frontline and who are subject to traumatic events such as illness and death are particularly at risk of stress responses when making increasingly difficult decision and their job is stressful generally.

Furthermore, Li et al., (2020) acknowledged how often people and medical staff suffer from vicarious traumatization and how this vicarious traumatization of non-front-line medical staff is more severe than that of front-line medical staff. The employee's efficiency and performance may also suffer as a result of traumatic situations. Holmes, et al, (2020) detailed that it would be meaningful to know if the workplace steps taken by employers will minimize employees fear and worry about Covid-19 and maintain reasonable work performances. In addition, low income people face job insecurities and financial insecurities, tight accommodations and limited internet and connectivity technologies. Job insecurity and loss of income is stressful since people are worried about how to provide for their families, pay accommodations and everyday expenses which worsen during this pandemic.

A research by Gunnel et al, (2020) identified that while an improvement in signs of anxiety and stress management is anticipated during these extraordinary circumstances, the prevalence of clinically relevant numbers of people with anxiety, depression and injuries (such as suicide and self-harm) is expected to increase. It is important to note that an increase in suicide is not unavoidable or uncontrolled, in particular with national efforts to mitigate it. According to Goyal et al., (2020) suicide is reported in India, as well as in other countries, including Italy, where two infected Italian nurses have committed suicide within few days of infection likely to be caused by fear of spreading Covid-19 to patients. It is likely to happen because of fear and anxiety about falling ill or spreading it to the loved ones in their families contributes to a rise in the suicide rate of 2020. In another study Kelvin & Rubino (2020) pointed out an issue about new symptoms of psychiatric which could arise or aggravate the disorder and anxiety of careers of the affected people in people without mental illness. People need to normalize asking others if they have been suffering from suicidal thoughts, it de-stigmatizes suicide as it becomes part of the everyday conversation.

Mitigating factors of Covid-19 on employee's mental health

Organizational factors

Covid-19 affected organizations either financially or to find other alternatives that supports the health measures (social distancing), work from home is one alternative to keep their businesses operating. This pandemic has demonstrated that decisions can be made faster without breaking the organization. Employers have the duty to ensure that during this pandemic their workplaces are safe. To avoid and monitor Covid-19, employers, employees and their organizations have to cooperate with health authorities. For workplace-related preventive initiatives, collaboration between management and staff and their representatives is important. International labor standards have to be completely upheld with regard to the rights and obligations of employees and employers in the area of occupational safety and health.

In this context, Hamouche (2020) demonstrated that employers, administrators have to work closely with practitioners of human resources and health organizations to establish a protection and health plan that can prevent the organization's risk of infection and coronavirus spread. In this sense, organizational strategies play an important role in mitigating the spread of the virus. For Brooks et al., (2018) all exposed and infected workers have to get assistance from their employers, which involves providing advices and other resources accessible to everyone in order to avoid emotional deterioration by employees, additionally employees would feel encouraged and secured by their employers.

Employers have to educate and train their employees about prevention habit and to provide them with appropriate safety material for those who need to be present in the workplace (e.g. masks, sanitizers, social distancing). As well, employees are responsible to post prevention recommendations (e.g. wash hands, avoid touching eyes, nose and mouth) Ramesh *et al.*, (2020). It is an added advantage for employers to have health care workers at the workplace in case of emergency and to ensure the temperature check up and make sure all the health care guidelines are in place and adhered to. If possible, employees need to be allowed to work from home and meetings have to be done via zoom or other communicating platforms in order to promote social distancing and further spread of the virus. No social stigma or workplace discrimination for any

cause, including access to information and safety from Covid-19, occupational health services, mental health and psychosocial support.

Teleworking

Before the pandemic, studies indicated that teleworking can increase the job satisfaction and commitment of workers to a company and even boost their performance at work slightly. On the other hand, teleworking is only possible for certain professions and not all, such as; teachers, accountants and other professions can telework but this is not applicable to nurses and doctors as they need to be present and communicating to patients in person. However, teleworking during the pandemic brings extra mental health challenges Hamouche (2020).

For those new to teleworking experience, lack of in-person collaboration with colleagues who do not have a home office or environment conducive to doing work may be the greatest challenge of working from home during the pandemic. With other family members present in homes, including children or spouse, preventing disturbances and interruptions may be almost impossible. Employees find themselves in uncomfortable role of carrying out meetings from their bedrooms or kitchens in order to find privacy. Moreover, it is not always easy to get virtual meeting technology to function properly. According to Tavares (2017), changes can lead to anxiety, stress and anger which tops to mental breakdown for employees. Even if there is no urgent business to discuss, managers need to consider holding a daily five minutes check in with each staff member, like trying to arrange virtual lunch and coffee sessions for colleagues to catch up with each other's projects and retain the relationships.

Occupational role

With the global dissemination of Covid-19, the importance of public health in quantifying who is at risk of contracting illness is persuasive. Occupational features, such as communicating with the public and working with other staffs, it does not only place workers on higher risks for contracting the disease but it hinders their health as well. Mostly the occupations that are at high risk of contracting the virus are the health workers and all essential workers who come in contact with infected people every day. These studies (Huang *et al.*, 2020; Zhu *et al.*, 2020) supported that their occupation is at high risk in terms of mental health during this. Other studies found out that most

health professionals working in isolation units and hospitals very often do not receive any training for providing mental health care (Lima et al., 2020). Occupations that are not on the essential call are on the risk of mental health breakdown though they are excused from their everyday role and not coming in contact with everyone, other stressors of Covid-19 such as financial loss, job insecurities, teleworking and social distancing are also challenging their mental health that is discussed further in the next subdivisions.

Individual factors

Quarantine

When Covid-19 emerged in China, late 2019, most citizens were home-quarantined to prevent the spread of the virus Wanjie et.al (2020). In recent pandemics, isolation and quarantine (more extreme forms of social distancing) have triggered depression and anxiety. Brooks et.al, (2020) supports that we might expect to see similar effects as confirmed people are detached from their loved ones, deprived of personal liberties, and devoid of purpose owing to altered routine and livelihood. This can contribute to frustration, boredom, low mood, and potentially depression. Those who are infected and affected by the virus are asked to go in quarantine to avoid further spread of the virus, though people in quarantine are going through mental disorder because they are scared of the deadly virus and all they think is death, 'maybe I am next'. There is so much going on in quarantine, many or few are thinking about the stigma and discrimination they will face after healing, others are focusing more on their financial lives. The pandemic has affected all the operations, things are tough for everyone during this pandemic and those who survive on hand to mouth have lost their income which is very stressful because of no cash inflow and fear for them to be removed from their rental accommodations and not able to provide food for their families.

Stigma and social exclusion

Social stigma in the sense of health is the derogatory correlation between an individual or group of people who share those characteristics and a particular illness. Stigma is not new in the history of pandemics, when Africa had Ebola, many of the Africans in other parts of the world experienced humiliation and name callings because of the virus, which caused mental breakdown. Stigma and social isolation have an effect on mental health, this can mean that individuals are branded,

stereotyped, discriminated against, treated individually in an outbreak or suffer loss of status due to a perceived association with a disease. The mental health of people with the disorder, as well as their caregivers, families, friends and communities, can be adversely affected by such treatment.

People who don't have the disease but share other characteristics with this group may also suffer from stigma. According to Nature Reviews Physics (2020) the current Covid-19 outbreak has provoked social stigma and discriminatory behaviors against people of certain ethnic backgrounds as well as anyone perceived to have been in contact with the virus. Knowing that the virus erupted first from China, Chinese citizens in different parts of the world experience stigma and name callings from other people that has affected their mental health and challenged their freedom and belongingness. Also, stigma and social exclusion exposed affected people to the loss of new connections and opportunities. Workplace strategies addressing stigma reduction need to be created or improved by organizations. The implementation of a zero-tolerance (anti-discrimination) policy for example Stewart (2018), is a powerful tool for protecting workers, preventing workers, preventing stigmatization and improving workplaces health and well-being.

Death

Covid-19 have caused many deaths in different countries affected by the pandemic as reported by (Worldometers, 2020). Death anxiety may indeed be a driving factor in everyday human behavior, it appears more relevant than ever in the context of the current pandemic that is contributing to mental health breakdown. Many people who do not receive proper counselling after their loved one or colleague's death, experience mental health difficulties as they fail to accept that, some get suicidal thoughts. According to Iverach et al., (2014) death anxiety has been proposed to be a trans diagnostic construct, underpinning a range of different mental health conditions. For instance, fears of death may manifest in the frequent reassurance seeking from doctors, checking of one's body, and requests for medical testing seen in the somatic symptom-related disorders.

For those grieving from the traumatic and sudden loss of loved ones from the outbreak, the inability to gain closure can result in anger and resentment (Shear,2012). Many of the deaths come from people, our families, our lovers, our mates, our neighbors, our colleagues and people we have never met all over the world. Funerals are still online and it is very uncomfortable in the hearts of

the affected one, as health workers do all the funeral services and people cannot pay their last respect to their loved one.

Social media mis-information

A study by Gao et al., (2020) reported that the social media could lead to an overburden (mis)information, which in return cause mental health problems. World Health Organization (2020) pointed out that it recognized the drivers of fear, anxiety and stigma, which fuel misinformation and rumors, especially on social media. Watching, reading or listening to Covid-19 news can cause one to feel nervous or distressed, individuals need to seek information only from reliable sources and primarily to take realistic actions to make their plans and protect themselves and loved ones. Moreover, to seek updates of verified data at particular times during the day, once or twice. The rapid and near constant influx of news stories about an outbreak will cause everyone to feel worried. People need to consider the fact that they need to keep an eye on credible outlets, not speculation and misinformation that can depress them.

Financial loss and job insecurity

The study Zhou et al., (2020) confirmed that pandemics have negative impacts on the individual's financial capacity due to the loss of income. Financial loss can be an issue from individuals who are quarantined, since they are not able to work or to maintain their professional activities Hamouche, (2020). The hardships presented here have many negative consequences for households. Experiencing difficulties like failure to paying rent put households and families at risk for eviction, especially when eviction delays some municipalities implemented expired and households struggle to pay back-due rent. The negative downstream effects of eviction are varied and far-reaching: loss of possessions, disruptive school changes, loss of friends for children, and mental health distress. The self-employed are also affected by the pandemic, this includes the street vendors who are working tirelessly to provide for their families as they survive more on hand to mouth and loosing income is one of the major causes to their mental health. Nobody is allowed to be on the streets that means nobody is going to sell as they have to obey to the government rules and health measures in place. This is also the same with the tourism industry which as well going through so much loss, no one is travelling or using their services and at the end they decided to

retrench employees because of lack of finance to keep them. Perceived job insecurity has been found to be a fundamental contributor to mental health breakdown during the Covid-19 outbreak, Zhou et al., (2020), as it has a negative impact on the individual's financial capacity due to the high risk of financial loss Irish Dental Association News (2020).

Tight accommodation

Agreeing to Zhou et.al, (2020) families are forced to live in crowded accommodations as they cannot afford the spacious ones, this pandemic led to loss of financial income and jobs as well as mortgage credit is tightening. Likewise, families are forced to live in accommodations that they can afford which do not have enough space for social distancing and self-quarantine. Having the fear that the virus can be spread from anyone either your spouse, child, sister or brother and sharing bedrooms have caused so much panic in many homes that led to mental health breakdown. Aforementioned stressors of Covid-19 that are affecting mental health are represented in the conceptual framework in the next division.

Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a structure which the researcher believes can best explain the natural progression of the phenomenon to be studied (Camp,2001)

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Showed Conceptual Framework on the Covid-19 effect on employees' mental health.
Source: authors construct

The framework shows that Covid-19 has caused so much effect at different roles, organizational role, individual roles and occupational roles, that led to employee's mental health breakdown. Covid-19 has impacted many organizations, that forced some to close and have financial loss, this had depressed employees for no job security. Some organizations came up with different ideas to keep businesses in succession, however they introduced teleworking which is not effective for everyone since employees are used to engage with one another in a physical contact. Different occupations are also a challenge because it is impossible for a mine worker to work from home since physical engagement is really the only thing they can do to perform better. Yet to the practical ones like teaching is also affected, this is a challenge to their mental health as there is so much disturbances in their homes, either their relatives or no work conducive environments. Organizations are going through tough times of financial crisis as they are now spending much on all the health precautions at the work places and not making any profit.

Covid-19 has an influence on occupational role, depending on the occupation that one is specialized in, some of the working places are not able to close because of the essential services that they offer every day. This includes; health workers, guard officers, fire fighters, electricians and many others. In addition, essential employees are on the higher risk of contracting the virus as they are needed to serve others and this have disturbed their mental health as they are scared to contract the virus in their everyday roles. The pandemic had put the whole world on lockdown which made infected and affected people go through quarantine, stigma and social exclusion, financial loss, job insecurity, death trauma, tight accommodation and fear to live again, these have dejected everyone. Receiving death news of the beloved one, colleague, neighbor is traumatizing and not easy to accept or get used to death as everyone is thinking maybe they are next to die.

Life is demanding and one needs capital to push through, many of those who lost income are finding it hard to feed their families and pay accommodations, some found out no purpose of living and ended their lives while the rest are battling with their mental health.

Methodology

The present study is completely based on literature reviews which focused on employees. The collected literature provided understanding about the impact of Covid-19 on employee's mental health. To survive this purpose authors selected secondary data such as journals, websites and reports to develop the entire paper. In addition, the study used library database such as Elsevier, Emerald, Springer, Scopus, Taylor & Francis and Wiley under science. The main keywords used for the research include; Covid-19, employees, mental health, workplace, depression, anxiety, mental health awareness. Internet search engines through google, Google scholars are utilized to identify and access the relevant working papers and reports are used to ensure comprehensive coverage of the literature. The target group for this study is all the employees around the globe during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Discussion

The identified literature reported a positive impact of Covid-19 on individual's mental health. Stressors include perception of safety, threat and risk of contagion, infobesity versus the unknown, quarantine and confinement, stigma and social exclusion as well as financial loss and job insecurity. A study identified that many health professionals working in isolation units and hospitals very often do not receive any training for providing mental health care (Lima et al., 2020). They need to educate and train their employees about prevention behaviors and to provide the required protection materials for those who need to be present in the workplace (e.g. masks, sanitizers and practicing social distancing).

The authors identified groups at increased risk of adverse effects in mental health such as Covid-19 patients and their families, people with existing physical or psychological conditions, and health

workers (Rajkumar, 2020). Some papers point out that the wide range and scope of Covid-19 could lead to a real mental health crisis, particularly in countries with high cases (Dong and Bouey, 2020), where both large - scale psychosocial problems are possible, and mental health care will in future be incorporated into disaster management plans. Good mental health is an advantage and is related to good physical health, both promoting positive, social and economic effects for individuals and society.

Mental health is a very great concern in everyone's life and it is employer's duties to provide safe working environment for their employees. The employers need to have mental health professionals, social workers, psychologists and counsellors to make everyone aware of mental health in the workplace for situations as this. Members of the health systems, emergency responders and healthcare professionals need to provide education and training on psychosocial issues. Mental health and emergency management need to be developed to identify and deliver evidence - based mental health, triage and treatment services. Data from the media and social networks should be closely monitored and therapeutic strategies sponsored by the government implemented internationally. Workplace measures need to promote and maintain the mental health and work performance of employees during the Covid-19 epidemic. The positive association between the number of measures and fear and worry about Covid-19 may reflect increased awareness about Covid-19 among employees resulted from taking the measures.

Employers must be watching their employees if they are keeping up with the counseling services, in order to make sure the well-being of their employees is safe. Managers and human resource practitioners must implement policies that are in support of their employees in situations like this.

Consistent with the reviews, Corona virus has an influence on employee's mental health. The pandemic has affected everyone and psychological concerns of the Covid-19 could be serious. Outbreaks of infectious diseases such as Covid-19 can be terrifying and affect employee's mental health. Although it is also important to be informed, we can also do other things in these days in order to support and maintain our well-being. This include the need to filter information we get from social media about the pandemic or to discover new hobbies to keep us busy. In every stage of life, from childhood and adolescence to adulthood, mental health is important. Throughout life,

thinking, mood and behavior can be affected if one is experiencing mental health problems as many factors contribute to mental health problems, such as life experiences.

Conclusion

In this paper a detailed review on the effect of Covid-19 pandemic on employee's mental health is nattered and all the stressors that come with a pandemic are discussed. The stressors can lead to distress, panic attacks, anxiety, depression and suicide. To combat with this situation in the future, however, employers need to have health care experts who are trained on mental health to help their employees psychologically fit for a time as this. Similarly, organizational productivity and employee's performance can be affected by poor mental health, therefore employers and human resource managers must include policies that focus on employee's mental health. Conversely, it is important that we do not neglect the psychological effect of the outbreak on individuals and society, which is often the limiting factor for the crisis to be resolved by the country. Well, after the outbreak has stopped, psychological complications may be long lasting and assistance should be provided.

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Dedication

This is a dedication to our grandparents, for their self-less love and made sure we have access to education. That is the perfect gift they gave us.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflict of interest to declare

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